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The Undernourishment Worldwide

Between 2013 and 2020 it grew by 8.9%

The World Bank calculates the percentage of the world's population undernourished. The prevalence of undernourishment is the percentage of the population whose usual food consumption is insufficient to supply the dietary energy levels necessary to maintain a normal, active, and healthy life. Data shown as 2.5 may indicate an undernourishment prevalence of less than 2.5%.

Ranking of countries by value of the percentage of the population undernourished globally in 2020. Somalia ranks first by value of the percentage of the population undernourished in 2020 with a value of 53.1, followed by the Central African Republic with a value of 52.2%, Madagascar with 48.5%, Haiti with 47.2%, North Korea with a value of 41.6%. In the middle of the table are Oman with a value of 9.8%, followed by Thailand with a value of 8.8%, Paraguay with a value of 8.7%, Peru with an amount of 8.3%, Colombia with 8.2%. Turkey, the United Kingdom, the United States, Uruguay and Uzbekistan close the ranking with 2.5%. On average in 2020 the percentage of undernourished population was equal to an amount of 10.2%.

Ranking of countries by value of the percentage change of the undernourished population worldwide between 2013 and 2020. Venezuela is in first place for growth of the undernourished population with a value equal to +816.00%, followed by Jordan with a value equal to 181.67%, from Mali with +164.86%, from Gambia with 120.41%, and from Lebanon with +118%. In the middle of the table are Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, and the United Kingdom with a value of 0%. The ranking is closed by Myanmar with -49.18%, followed by Sri Lanka with -51.43%, the Philippines with a value of -55.17%, the Ivory Coast with -55.56%, and Mongolia. Looking at the data, we can see that there are some countries for which the growth in malnutrition has been very significant, such as, for example, Venezuela which is experiencing a crisis linked to the civil war. However, among the countries in which the value of undernourished people has grown there are also three BRICS countries: South Africa with +60.47%, Brazil with +46.43% and India with +9.4%. Japan is the only country with a high per capita income in which there has been a growth in the percentage of the undernourished population with +28%. Among the countries that have significantly reduced the value of the percentage of the undernourished population are many Asian countries such as Mongolia, the Philippines, Sri Lanka, Myanmar, Vietnam, Cambodia, Bangladesh, Indonesia.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method is presented below. Six clusters are identified, namely:

- *Cluster 1:* Sri Lanka, Macao SAR, Nepal, South Africa, Mexico, Vanuatu, Ecuador, Dominica, St. Vincent and The Grenadines, Mauritius, Kyrgyz Republic, Cameroon, Nigeria, Jordan, Fiji, Lebanon, Senegal, El Salvador, Guyana, Lao PDR, Mongolia, Peru, Cote d'Ivoire, Philippines, New Caledonia, United Arab Emirates, Ghana, Colombia, Indonesia,

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- Brunei Darussalam, Trinidad and Tobago, Panama, Jamaica, Dominican Republic, Cambodia, Oman, Mauritania, Suriname, Belize, Vietnam, Paraguay, Benin, Thailand, Georgia;
- *Cluster 2:* Haiti, North Korea, Central African Republic, Yemen, Madagascar, Somalia, Liberia, Congo, Rwanda.
 - *Cluster 3:* Namibia, Togo, Botswana, Kenya, Afghanistan, Papua New Guinea, Mozambique, Tanzania, Lesotho, Chad, Timor Leste, Congo, Sierra Leone;
 - *Cluster 4:* Cabo Verde, Angola, Malawi, India, Gabon, Honduras, Djibouti, Guatemala, Bolivia, Pakistan, Ethiopia, Sao Tome and Principe, Bangladesh, Eswatini, Burkina Faso, Solomon Islands, Iraq, Nicaragua, The Gambia, Venezuela, Sudan.
 - *Cluster 5:* Slovak Republic, Iran, Albania, Egypt, Samoa, Barbados, Myanmar, Costa Rica, Saudi Arabia, Morocco, Mali, Serbia, French Polynesia, Turkmenistan, Kiribati, Malaysia, North Macedonia, Bulgaria, Argentina, Chile, Armenia, Algeria, Tunisia, Japan, Brazil, Ukraine, Finland, New Zealand, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russian Federation, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Belgium, Belarus, Azerbaijan, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Austria, Turkey, Australia, United Kingdom, United States, Netherlands, Canada, China, Montenegro, France, Denmark, Greece, Hong Kong, Hungary, Iceland, Czechia, Ireland, Israel, Estonia, Italy, Kazakhstan, Cyprus, South Korea, Kuwait, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Cuba, Croatia, Malta, Uruguay, Uzbekistan.

From the point of view of the median, we can note the following ordering of the clusters, namely: $C2=41.6 > C3=26.9 > C4=16.9 > C1=6.9 > C5=2.5$. From a geographical point of view, we can see that most of the countries with high levels of malnutrition are present in Central-Southern Africa and South Asia. Western countries, on the other hand, have low levels of undernourished population. In particular, Cluster 5 is made up almost entirely of Western countries except for Iran and Cuba.

Conclusions. Between 2013 and 2020, undernourishment grew by an average of 8% worldwide. It must be considered that malnutrition is still very present in the countries of the southern hemisphere, both in central-southern Africa, in Latin America and in southern Asia. However, the growth of the Asian economy has led to a significant reduction in the percentage of the undernourished population in Eastern countries. However, there are some outliers, as for example in the case of Japan, which despite being a country with a high per capita income, has been characterized by a significant growth in the undernourished population. It must be considered that the historical series available stops at 2020. It is probable that both covid 19 and the Russian-Ukrainian war have worsened the condition of international food supply chains, creating a growth in the percentage of the world population suffering from malnutrition. However, it must be considered that malnutrition is also very widespread in some countries that have an agricultural vocation. This circumstance suggests that undernourishment is not due to insufficient food production but rather to the inefficiency of distribution and the widespread inequality in access to resources that characterizes countries with medium-low per capita income. Furthermore, new biotechnologies offer the possibility of significantly increasing food production by offering the food industry the opportunity to overcome the "natural" limitations of resources. It follows that the growth of undernourishment is the manifestation of a growing inequality at a global level which is spreading from countries starting from countries with low per capita income.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

2013-2020 % Variation

